

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

Image Processing is a technique to enhance raw images received from cameras/sensors placed on space probes, aircraft and satellites or pictures taken in normal day-to-day life for various applications. An Image is a rectangular graphical object. Image processing involves issues related to image representation, compression techniques and various complex operations, which can be carried out on the image data. The operations that come under image processing are image enhancement operations such as sharpening, blurring, brightening, edge enhancement etc. Image processing is any form of signal processing for which the input is an image, such as photographs or frames of video; the output of image processing can be either an image or a set of characteristics or parameters related to the image. Most image-processing techniques involve treating the image as a two-dimensional signal and applying standard signal-processing techniques to it. Image processing usually refers to digital image processing, but optical and analogue image processing is also possible.

We propose a system for controlling the traffic light by image processing. The vehicles are detected by the system through images instead of using electronic sensors embedded in the pavement. A camera will be placed alongside the traffic light. It will capture image sequences. Image processing is a better technique to control the state change of the traffic light. It shows that it can decrease traffic congestion and avoids the time being wasted by a green light on an empty road. It is also more reliable in estimating vehicle presence because it uses actual traffic images. It visualizes the practicality, so it functions much better than those systems that rely on the detection of the vehicles' metal content.

1.1 PROBLEM DEFINITION

Due to the increasing of road networks and the number of vehicles, traffic monitoring becomes very important. This leads to the quick development of the Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) technologies. Compared to conventional techniques such as microwave detectors, vision-based systems acquire more information about the vehicles. One of these information is vehicle counting and determining the traffic flow. This can be very useful for traffic monitoring and guide the drivers for better driving routes through bypassing the congested roads.

1.2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Video surveillance has been an energetic study area in pattern analysis and machine intelligence, due to its vital position in helping surveillance intelligence and law enforcement agencies to battle alongside offence and criminal actions. The objective of a visual surveillance system is to identify object density and to lift appropriate action when density crosses the threshold. After the moving objects are detected, it is necessary behaviours can be suitably interpreted in the background of their identities and their connections with the traffic.

The conventional traffic signalling system are not adaptable to change in the amount of traffic. This paper solves the problem by making traffic signals smart enough to distinguish between the lanes which have different densities of traffic present in them. This project makes use of image processing with the help of stored data set of respective lane images and a microprocessor to compute an output.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper 1: Accurate Vehicle Counting Approach Based on Deep Neural Networks

Authors: Mohamed A. Abdelwahab, International Conference on Innovative Trends in Computer Engineering (ITCE)

Year: 2019

Description: Vehicle counting is considered one of the most important applications in traffic control and management. To count vehicles, synchronous vehicle detection and tracking should be carried out. Recently, detection via deep neural networks (DNN) has achieved good performance. However, exploiting the DNN efficiently for vehicle counting is still challenging.

In this paper, an efficient approach for vehicle counting employing DNN and KLT tracker is proposed. To decrease the time complexity, vehicles are detected via DNN every N-frames, N=15 for example. Trajectories are extracted by tracking corner points through the N-frames. Then an efficient algorithm is introduced to assign unique vehicle labels to their corresponding trajectories. The proposed results, performed on diverse vehicle videos, show that vehicles are accurately tracked and counted whatever they are detected one or more times by the DNN.

Paper 2: Implementation of Pixel Based Adaptive Segmenter method for tracking and counting vehicles in visual surveillance

Authors: Muhammad Brilliant Subaweh, Eri Prasetyo Wibowo, International Conference on Informatics and Computing (ICIC)

Year: 2016

Description: Computer vision has many applications that were implemented to the existing advance technology. Vehicle tracking and counting in video surveillance are one of them. Vehicle tracking allows the computer to detect and track the vehicles that capture through video surveillance. Afterwards vehicle counting allows the computer to count all of the vehicles on video. Background Subtraction is one of the methods to perform object tracking and counting process for the system. This research implements Pixel Based Adaptive Segmenter Model for Background Subtraction method to perform object tracking and counting. This research used video capture of visual surveillance and vehicles as an object to track and count. Result of this research is the system can track and count all vehicles on videos.

This research uses Pixel Base Adaptive Segmenter algorithm, OpenCV, and cvBlob as a main library to create the system. The reason is because OpenCV provide the function to allow detect object on image. Moreover, Pixel Base Adaptive Segmenter is a good algorithm for background subtraction because it has low computation cost, good for detecting object [19], and cvBlob provides some methods to get the centroid, the track and the ID of the moving objects.

Paper 3: Vehicle Count System based on Time Interval Image Capture Method and Deep Learning Mask R-CNN

Authors: Eduardo Jr Piedad; Tuan-Tang Le; Kimberly Aying; Fhenyl Kristel Pama; Ianny Tabale, (TENCON)

Year: 2019

Description: Traffic congestion is an undesirable problem for big cities especially in third world countries. Better policy planning and decision-making from the authority come from well-conducted practical research. In this study, a Vehicle Count System (VCS) using deep learning Mask R-CNN is developed to classify and count vehicles passing in a target street. A novel time interval image capture (TIIC) system is employed to the VCS instead of the typical real-time video streaming to avoid big data storage cost. To determine the effectiveness of the developed VCS, its output is compared to that of the conventional method from the manual recording of the passing vehicles. Four vehicle types - cars, motorbikes, trucks and buses are present in the 1800 real traffic images gathered from an actual field. As an initial stage, the developed tool performs satisfactorily in classifying and counting car-type vehicle with 97.62% accuracy in 10-hour testing. However, it fails to recognize motorbikes probably due to its relatively smaller pixel size compared to other vehicle types. The presence of jeeps confused the VCS. The real image dataset can be used as a basis for further development. The newly developed TIIC system can also be used in future research as a promising tool to replace real-time video streaming.

Paper 4: Compressed-Domain Highway Vehicle Counting by Spatial and Temporal Regression,

Authors: Zilei Wang ; Xu Liu ; Jiashi Feng ; Jian Yang ; HongSheng Xi , *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology*

Year: 2019

Description: Counting on-road vehicles in the highway is fundamental for intelligent transportation management. This paper presents the first highway vehicle counting method in compressed domain, aiming at achieving comparable estimation performance with the pixel-domain methods. Counting in compressed domain is rather challenging due to limited information about vehicles and large variance in vehicle numbers. To address this problem, we develop new low-level features to mitigate the challenge from insufficient information in compressed videos. The new proposed features can be easily extracted from the coding-related metadata. Then, we propose a hierarchical classification-based regression (HCR) model to estimate the number of vehicles from the compressed-domain low-level features for individual frame. HCR hierarchically divides the traffic scenes into different cases according to the density of vehicles such that the large variance of traffic scenes can be effectively captured. Beside the spatial regression in each frame, we propose a locally temporal regression model to further refine the counting results, which exploits the continuous variation characteristics of the traffic flow. We extensively evaluate the proposed method on real highway surveillance videos. The experimental results consistently show that the proposed method is very competitive compared with the pixel-domain methods, which can reach similar performance with much lower computational cost.

Paper 5: An SSD Algorithm Based on Vehicle Counting Method

Authors: Qiaoqian Chen; Na Huang; Jieming Zhou; Zhao Tan, 37th Chinese Control Conference (CCC)

Year: 2018

Description: Detecting and counting vehicles in transportation surveillance videos are essential for applications ranging from traffic queue detection to incident and vehicle identification. In this paper, we propose a vehicle counting method based on Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD). We perform vehicle detection, vehicle tracking and counting tasks via SSD. The SSD has the capacity to extract meaningful features of a blob of vehicles and predicting the location and classification of vehicles. Tracking moving vehicles can be achieved by comparing the blob of vehicles and measuring the minimal distance between two temporal pictures. Furthermore, given that the virtual coil method is easy to implement, we utilize this method to count the number of moving vehicles with fast speed. Finally, the experiment results are provided to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed method on counting vehicles with above 87% accuracy of real-time processing speed.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In the existing system a vehicle counting method based on Single Shot MultiBox Detector(SSD). We perform vehicle detection, vehicle tracking and counting tasks via SSD.

The SSD has the capacity to extract meaningful features of blob of vehicles and predicting the location and classification of vehicles.

Tracking moving vehicles can be achieved by comparing the blob of vehicles and measuring the minimal distance between two temporal pictures. Furthermore, given that the virtual coil method is easy to implement, we utilize this method to count the number of moving vehicles with fast speed.

3.1.1 DRAWBACKS OF EXISTING SYSTEM

- This system need of complex data augmentation also suggests it needs a large number of data to train.
- The information flows unidirectional and the classifier network cannot utilize other directional information.
- Execution time is more as compared to other machine learning algorithms.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

1. Detection and counting of the vehicles in traffic signals.
2. Predicting the scene class based on the spatial relationships among the vehicles of interest and contextually important objects.

This uses machine learning techniques to get a high degree of accuracy from what is called “training data”. Haar Cascades uses the Adaboost learning algorithm which selects a small number of important features from a large set to give an efficient result.

Haar Cascade Algorithm

Haar Cascade is a machine learning object detection algorithm used to identify objects in an image or video.

The algorithm has four stages:

1. Haar Feature Selection
2. Creating Integral Images
3. Adaboost Training
4. Cascading Classifier

Haar-Like Feature

Haar-Like is a rectangular simple feature that is used as an input feature for cascaded classifier. In there are some filters based on Haar-Like feature. By applying every one of these filters into one special area of the image, the pixel sums under white areas are subtracted from the pixel sums under the black areas. That is the weight of white and black area can be considered as “1” and “-1”, respectively.

Fig 3.1 Haar Features

AdaBoost Algorithm

AdaBoost algorithm (a machine learning meta-algorithm) in choosing features and improving the performance is repeatedly used. AdaBoost in order to construct a strong classifier combined many weak classifiers.

AdaBoost in the way that mixes a series of AdaBoost classifiers as a filter chain. Each filter is a separate AdaBoost classifier which consists of a few weak classifiers. If each of these filters in the acceptance region of the image shows the vehicle fails, this area is immediately classified as a non-vehicle. When a filter accepts an area of image as a vehicle, the area enters the next filter in the chain. If this area of the image passes all the chain filters successfully, it is classified as vehicle. In this algorithm, each cycle of boosting a feature among all other potential features is selected and in the end, the final classification will be a linear combines of the initial weak classification.

Integral Image

Integral image is a quick method for calculating the Haar-Like feature. has used this technique and they recognized which Haar-Like feature among the other image.

Integral image is sum of all pixel values. With integral image Haar-Like feature can be calculated quickly by simple addition and subtraction.

Integral images can be defined as two-dimensional lookup tables in the form of a matrix with the same size of the original image.

Cascaded Classifier

Cascaded classifier is used for fast rejection of error windows and improving the processing speed.

In every node of trees there is a non-vehicle branching, it means that the image will not be vehicle. By this technique the false negative rate is at least.

The cascade classifier consists of a collection of stages, where each stage is an ensemble of weak learners. If the label is positive, the classifier passes the region to the next stage. The detector reports an object found at the current window location when the final stage classifies the region as positive.

3.2.1 ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

Advantage of Haar Cascade Algorithm

- It achieves good performance for both accuracy and time complexity.
- Calculation speed due to the use of integral images.
- Quick detection and high efficiency.

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

A Feasibility Study is an analysis used in measuring the ability and likelihood to complete a project successfully including all relevant factors. It must account for factors that affect it such as economic, technology, legal and scheduling factors. The crucial purpose of this phase is to find the need and to define the problem that has to be solved. The key considerations are

- ✓ Economic feasibility
- ✓ Technical feasibility
- ✓ Social feasibility
- ✓ Operational feasibility

3.3.1 Economic feasibility

Economic feasibility determines whether the required software is capable of generating financial gains for the organization. Software is said to be economically feasible if it focuses on the issues listed below. The cost incurred on software development to produce long-term gains for the organization is necessary to consider the benefits that can be achieved by developing the software.

3.3.2 Technical Feasibility

Technical feasibility assesses the current resources (such as hardware and software) technology, which are required to accomplish user requirements in the software within the allocated time and budget. Ascertain the technology chosen for software development has a large number of users so that they can be consulted when problems arise or improvements are required.

3.3.3 Social Feasibility

Social feasibility addresses the effect that the proposed may have on the social system in the project environment. It must be identified that employees in the particular industries may have specific status symbols within the society.

The social impact analysis (or social feasibility assessment) can be a very important part of the general appraisal of PPP projects, since many infrastructure

initiatives cause severe adverse impacts on communities surrounding the site on which they are implemented.

Social impact analysis is an exercise aimed at identifying and analyzing such impacts in order to understand the scale and reach of the project's social impacts. It also ensures that these impacts are mitigated, to the extent possible, and fully considered in the green light decision.

3.3.4 Operational Feasibility

Operational feasibility refers to the measure of solving problems with the help of a new proposed system. It helps in taking advantage of the opportunities and fulfils the requirements as identified during the development of the project.

Operational feasibility is the measure of how well a proposed system solves the problems, and takes advantage of the opportunities identified during scope definition and how it satisfies the requirements identified in the requirements analysis phase of system development.

Operational feasibility reviews the willingness of the organization to support the proposed system. This is probably the most difficult of the feasibilities to gauge.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 System Architecture

System Architecture is a generic discipline to handle objects (existing or to be created) called “systems”, in a way that supports reasoning about the structural properties of these objects. The system architecture is a response to the conceptual and practical difficulties of the description and the design of complex systems.

Fig 4.1 System Architecture

4.2 UML Diagram

UML stands for Unified Modeling Language. UML is a standardized general-purpose modelling language in the field of object-oriented software engineering. The standard is managed and was created by, the Object Management Group.

The Unified Modeling Language is a standard language for specifying, Visualization, Constructing and documenting the artefacts of the software system, as well as for business modelling and other non-software systems.

The UML represents a collection of best engineering practices that have proven successful in the modelling of large and complex systems.

The UML is a very important part of developing objects oriented software and the software development process. The UML uses mostly graphical notations to express the design of software projects.

GOALS:

The primary goals in the design of the UML are as follows:

1. Provide users with a ready-to-use, expressive visual modelling Language so that they can develop and exchange meaningful models.
2. Provide extensibility and specialization mechanisms to extend the core concepts.
3. Be independent of particular programming languages and development process.
4. Provide a formal basis for understanding the modelling language.
5. Encourage the growth of OO tools market.
6. Support higher-level development concepts such as collaborations, frameworks, patterns and components.
7. Integrate best practices.

4.2.1 Use Case Diagram

A use case diagram is a set of scenarios that describes interactions between a user and a system. A use case diagram displays the relationship among the actors and use cases. The two main components of a use case diagram are use cases and actors. An actor represents a user or another system that will interact with the system modelled. A use case is an external view of the system that represents some action.

Fig 4.2 Use Case Diagram

4.2.2 Class Diagram

Class diagram in the UML is a type of static structure diagram that describes the structure of a system's classes, their attributes, operations and the relationships among objects. Private visibility hides information from anything outside the class partition. Public visibility allows all other classes to view the marked information. Protected visibility allows child classes to access information they inherited from a parent class.

Fig 4.3 Class Diagram

4.2.3 Sequence Diagram

A sequence diagram in UML is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how the processes operate with one another and in what order. Sequence diagrams are typically associated with use case realizations in the logical view of the system under development. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams or event scenarios

Fig 4.3 Sequence Diagram

4.2.4 ActivityDiagram

Activity diagrams are graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modeling Language, activity diagrams can be used to describe the business and operational step-by-step workflows of components in a system. An activity diagram shows the overall flow of control.

Fig 4.4 Activity Diagram

4.3 Data Flow Diagram

Level 0

Level 1

Level 2

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The most common set of requirements defined by any operating system or software application is the physical computer resources, also known as hardware. A hardware requirements list is often accompanied by a hardware compatibility list, especially in case of operating systems. The minimal hardware requirements are as follows,

- PROCESSOR : PENTIUM IV
- RAM : 8 GB
- PROCESSOR : 2.4 GHZ
- MAIN MEMORY : 8GB RAM
- PROCESSING SPEED : 600 MHZ
- HARD DISK DRIVE : 1TB

5.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Software requirements is a field within software engineering that deals with establishing the needs of stakeholders that are to be solved by software. A software requirements specification (SRS) is a comprehensive description of the intended purpose and environment for software under development

Operating System : Windows 8 and above

Coding Language : Python

Tool & IDE : Anaconda

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1.1 Python Language

Python is an object-oriented programming language created by Guido Rossum in 1989. It is ideally designed for rapid prototyping of complex applications. It has interfaces to many OS system calls and libraries and is extensible to C or C++. Many large companies use the Python programming language include NASA, Google, YouTube, BitTorrent, etc. Python programming is widely used in Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Generation, Neural Networks and other advanced fields of Computer Science. Python had deep focus on code readability & this class will teach you python from basics.

Python Programming Characteristics

- It provides rich data types and easier to read syntax than any other programming languages
- It is a platform independent scripted language with full access to operating system API's
- Compared to other programming languages, it allows more run-time flexibility
- It includes the basic text manipulation facilities of Perl and Awk
- A module in Python may have one or more classes and free functions
- Libraries in Python are cross-platform compatible with Linux, Macintosh, and Windows
- For building large applications, Python can be compiled to byte-code
- Python supports functional and structured programming as well as OOP
- It supports interactive mode that allows interacting Testing and debugging of snippets of code

- In Python, since there is no compilation step, editing, debugging and testing is fast.

6.1.2 About Opencv Package

Python is a general purpose programming language started by Guido van Rossum, which became very popular in short time mainly because of its simplicity and code readability. It enables the programmer to express his ideas in fewer lines of code without reducing any readability.

Compared to other languages like C/C++, Python is slower. But another important feature of Python is that it can be easily extended with C/C++. This feature helps us to write computationally intensive codes in C/C++ and create a Python wrapper for it so that we can use these wrappers as Python modules. This gives us two advantages: first, our code is as fast as original C/C++ code (since it is the actual C++ code working in background) and second, it is very easy to code in Python. This is how OpenCV-Python works, it is a Python wrapper around original C++ implementation.

And the support of Numpy makes the task more easier. Numpy is a highly optimized library for numerical operations. It gives a MATLAB-style syntax. All the OpenCV array structures are converted to-and-from Numpy arrays. So whatever operations you can do in Numpy, you can combine it with OpenCV, which increases number of weapons in your arsenal. Besides that, several other libraries like SciPy, Matplotlib which supports Numpy can be used with this.

So OpenCV-Python is an appropriate tool for fast prototyping of computer vision problems.

6.1.3 Anaconda

Anaconda is a free and open source, easy to install distribution of Python and R programming languages. Anaconda provides a working environment which is used for scientific computing, data science, statistical analysis and machine learning.

The latest distribution of Anaconda is Anaconda 5.3 and is released in October, 2018. It has the conda package, environment manager and a collection of 1000+ open source packages long with free community support.

What is Anaconda Navigator?

Anaconda Navigator is a desktop graphical user interface (GUI) included in the Anaconda distribution. It allows us to launch applications provided in the Anaconda distribution and easily manage conda packages, environments and channels without the use of command-line commands. It is available for Windows, macOS and Linux.

Anaconda Navigator

Applications Provided In Anaconda Distribution

The Anaconda distribution comes with the following applications along with Anaconda Navigator.

1. JupyterLab
2. Jupyter Notebook
3. Qt Console
4. Spyder
5. Glueviz
6. Orange3
7. RStudio
8. Visual Studio Code

6.2 LIST OF MODULES

- **Data Preprocessing**
- **Feature Extraction**
- **Sliding Window**
- **Algorithm Implementation and Execution**

1. Data Preprocessing

It is a technique that is used to convert the raw data into a clean data set. In other words, whenever the data is gathered from different sources it is collected in raw format which is not feasible for the analysis.

Data goes through a series of steps during preprocessing:

Data Cleaning: Data is cleansed through processes such as filling in missing values, smoothing the noisy data, or resolving the inconsistencies in the data.

Data Integration: Data with different representations are put together and conflicts within the data are resolved.

Data Transformation: Data is normalized, aggregated and generalized.

Data Reduction: This step aims to present a reduced representation of the data in a data warehouse.

2. Feature extraction

It is the process of transforming the raw pixel values from an image, to a more meaningful and useful information that can be used in other techniques, such as point matching or machine learning.

In feature extraction module, we will characterize the boxes associated with vehicles by a set of

parameters. This step aims to perform two important tasks:

- Classify vehicles according to their types.
- Detect partial occlusions of vehicles.

Classification process is based on preliminary study applied to a vehicle image database in order to determine feature values associated with vehicle types. Thus, each vehicle detected in the first phase is classified depending on the values of the calculated parameters. In the last module, these vehicles are counted during their movement in the scene.

Background Subtraction

Background subtraction is a concept that belongs to areas like image processing and computer vision. Background subtraction is also known as the foreground detection. This technique is widely used to detect moving objects from video. In this technique, foreground of an image is extracted for further processing. It is the process of separating out foreground object of an image from the background in frames of video sequence.

Edges essentially separate two various regions which are static region (the roadway) and dynamic region (moving vehicles). The static background is then deleted to locate moving objects in each frame. The result zone leaves only vehicles and some details as moving objects in sequential images which are changing frame to frame.

Edge Detection

Each image (video frame) has three significant features to achieve detection goals. These features include: edges, contours and points. Among mentioned features, an appropriate option is to use edge pixels. Processing of image pixels enables us to find edge pixels, which are the main features of passing vehicles in a roadway video frame.

Edge detection process is demonstrated in a binary image (threshold) with the detected edge pixels.

The next step is to extract moving edges from sequential video frames and process the resulting edge information to obtain quantitative geometric measurements of passing vehicles.

3. Sliding Windows

Object detection using sliding window machine learning algorithm, first requirement of sliding window algorithm is to prepare labeled training set. Sliding window is a problem solving technique for problems involves arrays/lists.

The idea is to train a binary classifier, which determines if the presented object is “positive” or “negative.” The trained classifier can then be used to “inspect” a target image by sampling it, starting from the top-left corner

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 GENERAL

Testing is performed to identify errors. It is used for quality assurance. Testing is an integral part of the entire development and maintenance process. The goal of the testing during phase is to verify that the specification has been accurately and completely incorporated into the design, as well as to ensure the correctness of the design itself.

For example, the design must not have any logical faults. The fault in the design is detected before coding commences, otherwise the cost of fixing the faults will be considerably higher as reflected. Detection of design faults can be achieved by means of inspection as well as walkthrough.

7.2 TYPES OF TESTING

All field entries must work properly. Pages must be activated from the identified link. The entry screen, messages and response must not be delayed. There are many types of testing tools used for testing the documents for correctness.

7.2.1 UNIT TESTING

Unit testing is conducted to verify the functional performance of each modular component of the software. Unit testing focuses on the smallest unit of the software design (i.e.), the module. The white-box testing techniques were heavily employed for unit testing.

7.2.2 INTEGRATION TESTING

Integration testing is a systematic technique for constructing the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing i.e., integration testing is the complete testing of the set of modules which makes up the product. The objective is to take untested modules and build a program structure tester should identify critical modules.

7.2.3 FUNCTIONAL TESTING

Functional test cases involved exercising the code with normal input values for which. The expected results were known as well as boundary values and special values, such as logically related inputs, files of identical elements, and empty files.

Three types of tests in functional test:

- Performance Test
- Stress Test
- Structure Test

7.2.4 PERFORMANCE TESTING

It determines the amount of execution time spent in various parts of the unit, program throughput, and response time and device utilization by the program unit.

7.2.5 STRESS TESTING

Stress test is those test designed to intentionally break the unit. A great deal can be learned about the strength and limitations of a program by examining the manner in which a program unit breaks.

7.2.6 STRUCTURED TESTING

Structured testing are concerned with exercising the internal logic of a program and traversing particular execution paths. The way in which White-box testing strategy was employed to ensure that the test cases could guarantee that all independent paths within a module have been exercised at least once.

- Exercise all logical decisions on their true or false side.
- Execute all loops at their boundaries and within their operational bounds.
- Exercising internal data structures to assure their validity.
- Checking attributes for their correctness.
- Handling end of the file condition, I/O errors, buffer problems and textual errors in output information.

7.2.7 WHITE BOX TESTING

This testing is also called as Glass box testing. In this testing, by knowing the specific functions that a product has been designed to perform test can be conducted that demonstrate each function is fully operational at the same time searching for errors in each function. It is a test case design method that uses the control structure of the procedural design to derive test cases. Basis path testing is white box testing.

- Basis path testing:
- Flow graph notation
- Cyclometric complexity
- Deriving test cases
- Graph matrices control

7.2.8 BLACK BOX TESTING

In this testing by knowing the internal operation of a product, test can be conducted to ensure that “all gears mesh”, that is the internal operation performs according to specification and all internal components have been adequately exercised. It fundamentally focuses on the functional requirements of the software. The steps involved in black box test case design are:

- Graph based testing methods
- Equivalence partitioning
- Boundary value analysis
- Comparison testing

Test Case Results

Test	Test Requirements	Action	Expected Result	Actual Result	Pass/Fail
1	Cascade Classifier Training	Training the setup	Generate a Classified test set	An XML file generated	Pass
2	Feature extraction	Feature Extraction of the given positive images	Identify the image in the positive image set	Generated XML file identify the object in source	Pass
3	AdaBoost Training	Train the algorithm for faster detection	Reduce haar cascade generation significantly	Faster generation of haar cascade	Pass
4	Object density	Count the number of object on the image	Display the number of vehicles in source	Output the number of vehicles	Pass

Table 7.1 : Test Case Results

CHAPTER 8

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The system will automate the current traffic system based on the object or vehicle density on the given road. The proposed system uses Haar Cascade Algorithm and will start capturing video frame by frame per second (eg. 20 fps), and will start determining the density on all four lanes.

Haar Cascade Algorithm adaptation is faster and requires less data set as compared to presently available SSD (Single Shot Multibox Detector) which uses large data set for density determination.

The project may be very well used in where the traffic signals is kept and in many other places where we need to full fill the need of the automation. In this project we have studied the optimization of traffic light controller in a City using IR sensors and Arduino . Figure-4. Shows the complete circuit diagram of Arduino board. By using this system configuration we tries to reduce the possibilities of traffic jams, caused by traffic lights, to an extent and we have successfully gets the results.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

9.1 CONCLUSION

Vehicle counting is considered one of the most important applications in traffic control and management. To count vehicles, synchronous vehicle detection and tracking should be carried out. Preliminary results for developing an automated system for counting and classification of vehicles in motion, based on machine learning techniques were presented in this paper. The developed system was able to count vehicles and classify them with a reasonable accuracy.

There is exigent need of efficient traffic management system in our country, as India meets with 384 road accidents every day. To reduce this congestion and unwanted time delay in traffic an advanced system is designed here in this project. With field application of this technology, the maddening chaos of traffic can be effectively channelized by distributing the time slots based on the merit of the vehicle load in certain lanes of multi junction crossing. We have successfully implemented the prototype at laboratory scale with remarkable outcome. The next step forward is to implement this schema is real life scenario for first hand results, before implementing it on the largest scale. We believe that this may bring a revolutionary change in traffic management system on its application in actual field environment

9.2 FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

In Future sensors, processors and CCTV cameras can be implemented with increased image resolution provides the basis for a continuous growth of this field.

Future projects can include emergency condition like accident and ambulance detection at the signal, allowing those vehicle to let pass first in the given lane.

APPENDICES:

A.Sample Code

Car Classification

```
import cv2

print('Project Topic : Vehicle Classification')

print('Research Internship on Machine learning using Images')

cascade_src = 'cars.xml'

video_src = 'video.avi'

cap = cv2.VideoCapture(video_src)

car_cascade = cv2.CascadeClassifier(cascade_src)

while True:

    ret, img = cap.read()

    if (type(img) == type(None)):

        break

    gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)

    cars = car_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray, 1.1, 2)

    for (x,y,w,h) in cars:

        cv2.rectangle(img,(x,y),(x+w,y+h),(0,255,255),2)

    cv2.imshow('video', img)

    if cv2.waitKey(33) == 27:

        break

cv2.destroyAllWindows()
```

Bus Classification

```
import cv2
```

```

cascade_src = 'Bus_front.xml'
video_src = 'bus1.mp4'
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(video_src)
car_cascade = cv2.CascadeClassifier(cascade_src)
while True:
    ret, img = cap.read()
    if (type(img) == type(None)):
        break
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
    cars = car_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray, 1.16, 1)
    for (x,y,w,h) in cars:
        cv2.rectangle(img,(x,y),(x+w,y+h),(0,0,255),2)
    cv2.imshow('video', img)
    if cv2.waitKey(33) == 27:
        break
cv2.destroyAllWindows()

```

Pedestrian Classification

```

import cv2

video_src = 'pedestrians.avi'
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(video_src)
bike_cascade = cv2.CascadeClassifier('pedestrian.xml')
while True:
    ret, img = cap.read()

```

```

if (type(img) == type(None)):
    break

gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
bike = bike_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray,1.3,2)
for(a,b,c,d) in bike:
    cv2.rectangle(img,(a,b),(a+c,b+d),(0,255,210),4)
cv2.imshow('video', img)
if cv2.waitKey(33) == 27:
    break
cv2.destroyAllWindows()

```

Bus Classification

```

import cv2

print('Project Topic : Vehicle Classification')

cascade_src = 'Bus_front.xml'
video_src = 'bus1.mp4'
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(video_src)
car_cascade = cv2.CascadeClassifier(cascade_src)

while True:
    ret, img = cap.read()
    if (type(img) == type(None)):
        break
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)

```

```
cars = car_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray, 1.16, 1)

for (x,y,w,h) in cars:
    cv2.rectangle(img,(x,y),(x+w,y+h),(0,0,255),2)
cv2.imshow('video', img)
if cv2.waitKey(33) == 27:
    break
cv2.destroyAllWindows()
```

B. Screenshots

Normal Case

Skip Lane Case

Extended Time Case

No Vehicle Around Case

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